

The Action of Acids and Water upon Magnesium Boride.

BY

RAMES CHANDRA RAY.

In his systematic researches on the action of magnesium on oxygen compounds, Winckler (Ber., 1890, 23, 722) studied the reaction between magnesium and boron trioxide, and from the results of analyses of the products of the reaction, he drew the conclusion that two borides were formed, one having the formula Mg_3B_2 and the other Mg_5B_3 . Moissan [Compt. rend., 1892, 114, 392; also Ann. Chim. Phys., 1895 (VII), 6, 296] has also mentioned of two borides of magnesium one of which was unstable and decomposable by water and the other did not react either with water or with hydrochloric or nitric acid. The latter substance was obtained in a crystalline form. The crystalline substance, which Moissan supposed to be another magnesium boride, appears to be crystalline boron, a certain amount of which is always formed in the preparation of magnesium boride, depending upon the temperature and duration of heating. It has been shown in a previous communication (Jour. Chem. Soc., 1914, 105, 2162) that at a red heat and under normal pressure only one boride having the formula, Mg_3B_2 , is formed, and on heating the boride, magnesium is driven off and the greater part of the boron separates in the crystalline state. On heating the so-called amorphous boron with magnesium the same boride, with a small quantity of magnesium oxide, is obtained.

The product obtained by heating a mixture of 1 part of boron trioxide and 2.2 parts of magnesium powder to a

red-heat in a current of hydrogen for 45 minutes was almost completely soluble in dilute hydrochloric acid, and appeared, from the results of analyses, to consist of magnesium boride, Mg_2B_3 , and magnesium oxide in the theoretical proportions. One of the samples of crude boride, prepared in the abovementioned manner, was found to consist of:—

Magnesium	...	...	64.71 per cent.
Boron as boride (soluble in dilute HCl)	...	...	8.72 " "
Residue insoluble in dilute HCl (free boron, etc.)	...	...	2.46 " "
Oxygen (by difference)	...	...	24.11 " "

and one gram yielded, when dissolved in acid, 0.0472 gram of hydrogen, whilst one gram of a substance containing 8.72 per cent. of boron as the boride Mg_2B_3 should yield 0.0476 gram of hydrogen according to the equation:—

Jones (Trans. Chem. Soc., 1879, 35, 41) and two years later, Jones and Taylor (*ibid.*, 1881, 39, 213) studied the action of hydrochloric acid on magnesium boride. They obtained a gaseous boron hydride to which they assigned the formula BH_3 , but they could not isolate it from the large quantity of hydrogen which was evolved at the same time. Their work was confirmed in a qualitative manner by Sabatier (Compt. rend., 1891, 112, 866). Ramsay and Hatfield (Proc. Chem. Soc., 1901, 17, 152) found that on passing the gas evolved by the action of dilute acids on magnesium boride through a bulb cooled in liquid air, a solid substance was deposited which, when the bulb was warmed, volatilised and could be collected as a gas. From the results of analyses of the gas, and its density, its formula appeared to be B_2H_4 ; but it appeared to consist of two isomeric substances, one stable and the other unstable and readily decomposed by

reagents. Ramsay and Hatfield, however, were subsequently unable to duplicate the work.

Stock and his co-workers (Stock and Massenez, Ber., 1912, 45, 3539; Stock and Friederici, *ibid*, 1913, 46, 1959; Stock, Friederici and Priess, *ibid*, 1913, 46, 3353; Stock, Zeits. Electrochem, 1913, 19, 779; Stock, Kuss and Priess, Ber., 1914, 47, 3115; Stock and Kuss, Ber., 1923, 56 [B] 780) succeeded in isolating several boron hydrides by dropping finely powdered magnesium boride into 15 per cent. hydrochloric acid at 50° to 80°. According to them at least ten boron hydrides exist, of which they have obtained the following in a pure condition:—

(a) B_2H_8 (B.p.-91°), (b) B_4H_{10} (B.p.-18°), (c) B_5H_9 (liquid; Vap. Press. at 0° 64 mm.), (d) B_6H_{10} (liquid Vap. Press. at 0° 7 mm.), (e) $B_{10}H_{14}$ (crystalline solid; M.p. 99°).

In spite of careful examination they have failed to find the slightest indication of a boron hydride containing one atom of boron in the molecule. They have also shown that all the boron hydrides react with water with the formation of boric acid and liberation of hydrogen.

It has already been shown that when magnesium boride is treated with dilute acids, and the gases evolved kept in contact with the acid for a short time, the residual gas contains only hydrogen. Boric acid and the magnesium salt of the acid employed in the reaction are found in the solution, and for every molecule of magnesium boride, Mg_3B_2 , six molecules of hydrogen are evolved. It appears probable that the boron hydride or hydrides which are first formed by the action of the acid on magnesium boride, are completely decomposed by the action of water. The failure of the earlier workers in preparing boron hydrides is perhaps mainly attributable to this cause.

The action of water on magnesium boride, on the other hand, appears to be entirely different. When

water is added to magnesium boride, which always contains a certain amount of magnesium oxide, the reaction takes place with evolution of a considerable quantity of heat, and hydrogen is liberated, containing only traces of boron hydrides, which impart to it a characteristic unpleasant odour, but no boric acid or magnesium borate is formed in the reaction. The amount of hydrogen given off by the action of water is only one-half of that liberated by the action of dilute acid. The solution contains only a small quantity of boron as borohydrates, the properties of which have been described by Travers, Ray and Gupta (Pamphlet, H. K. Lewis & Co., London, 1916).

A sample of magnesium boride was prepared by heating amorphous boron (a chocolate brown powder) with magnesium powder in a magnesia-lined crucible, a rapid current of hydrogen being passed into it from the commencement of the experiment until the crucible was cold. The magnesium boride gave, on analyses, the following results:—

Insoluble (crystalline boron, etc.)	...	0.76	per cent.
Magnesium	...	74.13	„ „
Boron (soluble in acid)	...	18.76	„ „
Oxygen (by difference)	...	6.35	„ „
Magnesium as oxide	...	9.51	„ „
Magnesium as boride	...	64.62	„ „
Boron as boride	...	18.76	„ „

It was treated with water and the hydrogen evolved was collected and measured. A weighed quantity of the substance was introduced into a flask and a measured volume of water was added to it. The mouth of the flask was quickly closed with a rubber stopper provided with a delivery tube, dipping under water. The volume of hydrogen evolved was measured from time to time. When the rate of evolution of hydrogen fell to less than 3 c.c. per gram of boride in twenty-four hours the

experiment was brought to an end. The following results were obtained:—

Time in hours	...	20	40	60	90	114	138	186	258	306	426
Volume of hydrogen in c.c. at N T. P. per gram of boride	...	144	204	286	345	402	440	480	512	528	543

During the experiment the water in contact with the boride was changed several times and the amount of boron in each of the solutions was estimated. The total quantity of boron removed as soluble borohydrate in the course of the experiment was approximately 0.02 gram per gram of boride. One gram of the boride contained 0.1876 gram of boron as boride, so that only 10 per cent. of the boron in the magnesium boride went into solution as borohydrates.

The results are plotted in Fig. 1. It will be observed

Fig. 1.

that the rate of evolution of hydrogen is very rapid at first, gradually falls off, and finally reaches a limiting value. The total quantity of hydrogen evolved after 426 hours is 543 c.c. or 0.0489 gram per gram of boride and this amount very nearly approaches the limiting value of the quantity of hydrogen which would be evolved on treating the boride with water for a very long time, that is, until the reaction is complete. One gram of the boride when treated with dilute hydrochloric acid gave off 0.1040 gram of hydrogen, and one-half of this quantity, 0.0520 gram is very nearly equal to the amount of hydrogen liberated by the action of water. The slightly lower value actually obtained is probably due to the fact that the reaction between water and the boride was not quite complete. The reaction of water on magnesium boride has been studied more fully in collaboration with Travers and Gupta (*loc. cit.*). From the amount of hydrogen evolved per gram of magnesium boride and analyses of the residue from action of water on the boride, it has been shown that the reaction takes place according to the equation:—

That this is mainly the reaction, which takes place between water and magnesium boride, has been proved by the action of dilute hydrochloric acid and ammonia on the "spent boride." The product of the reaction with water appears to be completely insoluble in and inactive towards both hot and cold water and may be regarded as the magnesium salt of a borohydrate of the formula

It is not improbable that, as shown by Schwarz and Konrad (Ber., 1922, 55, [B], 3242) in the case of the action of water on magnesium silicide, Mg_2Si , the first product of decomposition is a compound of the formula

$H_2B_3(Mg.OH)_3$, and the reaction may be expressed by the equation :—

This primary product then suffers further hydrolysis which may be represented by the equation:

About 90 per cent. of the initial product undergoes decomposition according to equation (3) which is the main reaction between water and magnesium boride. The formation of borohydrates and hydroborons, which are undoubtedly produced by secondary reactions, probably takes place according to the following scheme :—

and

Only about 10 per cent. of the magnesium boride or the primary product of the action of water upon it undergoes decomposition according to the equation (4) or (5), and this accounts for the small yield of borohydrates or hydroborons obtained in the reactions with water or acids. Contrary to what has been generally supposed no boric acid or magnesium borate is formed in the reaction with water. The formation of boric acid takes place by the decomposition of the compound $Mg_3B_2(OH)_6$ according to the equation :—

or by the decomposition of the hydrides of boron, all of which, as has been shown by Stock and his collaborators (*loc. cit.*), react readily with water with evolution of hydrogen and formation of boric acid.

Summary.

(1) When magnesium boride is treated with water the quantity of hydrogen liberated is only one-half of

that obtained by the action of dilute acids upon it. In the reaction between water and magnesium boride, no boric acid or magnesium borate is formed.

(2) The mechanism of the action of water and dilute acids upon magnesium boride, and of the formation of borohydrates and hydrides of boron, has been suggested.

The author's best thanks are due to Prof. F. G. Donnan, F.R.S., and to Dr. M. W. Travers, F.R.S., for their kind interest and helpful criticisms.

CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PATNA COLLEGE,
MORADPUR, BANKIPORE.
